

A Hospital Based Clinical Study Assessing Functional Outcome with Different Modalities in Fixation of Proximal Humerus Shaft Fractures**Rupesh Kumar¹, Anjana², Shashikant Singh³**¹Associate Professor, Department of Orthopaedics, Sheikh Bhikhari Medical College, Hazaribagh, Jharkhand, India²Tutor, Department of Pathology, Sheikh Bhikhari Medical College, Hazaribagh, Jharkhand, India³Assistant professor, Department of Orthopaedics, Sheikh Bhikhari Medical College, Hazaribagh, Jharkhand, India

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract**Aim:** The aim of the present study was to assess and compare the functional outcome with different modalities in fixation of proximal humerus shaft fractures.**Methods:** The present retrospective study was conducted in the Department of Orthopaedics for a period of 1 year. 50 cases who fulfilled the inclusion criteria were enrolled.**Results:** 46% of the cases were between 41-60 years with 32% between <18-40 years and 22% of cases >60 years of age. The age range was from 19 to 68 years with a mean age of 48.2 years. 52% of cases were females and 48% were males. 64% of the cases sustained fracture on the left side and 36% on right side. 84% of fractures were of closed type and 16% were open. As per Neer's type of fracture classification, the most common type of fracture observed in our study cases was two-part fracture accounting to 40% of cases followed in order by three part (26%), four part observed in 24% of cases. 5 cases (10%) had fracture dislocation. Road traffic injury was the most common mechanism for injury in 60% of cases and next was a history of fall in 32% of cases and one case was electric shock and other was hit by an iron rod. 23 cases (46%) were managed by open reduction and internal fixation with locking compression plate using 4.5 mm cortical screw plates and 6.5 mm cancellous screws. Percutaneous pinning was done in 10 cases (20%). Open reduction with K-wire was done in 6 cases (12%) and open reduction with K-wire and cancellous screws in 3 cases (6%). Closed reduction with intramedullary nailing was done in 4 cases (8%). The mean scores observed on Neer's score were pain (34.6 units), function (23.5 units), range of motion (16.55 units) and anatomy (6.9 units).**Conclusion:** The present study concluded that good surgical skills, surgeons experience in selection of the type of surgery depending upon the factors like type of fracture are necessary to achieve correct and best outcome. Clinical evaluation, obtaining proper radiological views, age of the patient and activity holds the key for realistic approach and surgical management of complex humerus fractures.**Keywords:** Neer's score, Humerus fracture, Range of motion, Functional outcome.This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.**Introduction**

Fractures of the proximal humerus represent approximately 4% of all fractures and 26% of humerus fractures. These are the second most common upper- extremity fracture and the third most common fracture, after hip and distal radial fractures. [1] The distribution of humeral fracture according to age is typical with high velocity trauma being the common cause among young individuals and a simple fall in older individuals because of osteoporosis. [2] The fractures can occur at any age, but the incidence rapidly increases with age. The risk factors for proximal humeral fractures are primarily associated with low bone mineral density and an increased risk of falls.

The most common mechanism of injury in proximal humeral fractures in elderly patients is a fall from standing height onto an outstretched upper extremity. In patients aged less than 50 years, the mechanism is often related to high-energy trauma, such as significant falls from height, motor vehicle accidents, or athletic injuries.

The injury is of great importance when it affects the young and middle age groups of the population. It leads to temporary disability and loss of working hours. Restoration of the function of the limb is of paramount importance. Treatment of proximal humerus fracture has been the subject of much controversy and confusion. This is because of the

complexity of these injuries, fracture displacements are without careful radiographic views and associated soft tissue injuries. Further, there has always been diversity of opinion about the care of shoulder fractures, with frequent controversies and lively debate, further more even good anatomical results achieved at operative repair may lead to poor results unless there is meticulous post-operative rehabilitation, which can be more challenging in shoulder than operative technique. [2-4] Majority of these fractures are stable, minimally displaced or nondisplaced and mostly managed by nonoperative techniques like immobilization, splints and casts etc. However, these techniques are associated with complications and disabilities like avascular necrosis, nonunion and malunion. [5] Treatment of proximal humerus fracture has been the subject of much controversy and confusion. This is because of the complexity of these injuries, fracture displacements without careful radiographic views and associated soft tissue injuries. [5] This is because of the complexity of these injuries, fracture displacements without careful radiographic views and associated soft tissue injuries. Further, there has always been diversity of opinion about the care of shoulder fractures, with frequent controversies and lively debate. Furthermore even good anatomical results achieved at operative repair may lead to poor results unless there is meticulous post-operative rehabilitation, which can be more challenging in shoulder than operative technique. [2-4]

With increase in the incidence of upper humerus fractures and advances in the techniques of surgery most of the surgeons prefer an operative management than conservative management. The various surgical modalities used are transosseous suture fixation, closed reduction and percutaneous fixation, open reduction and internal fixation with conventional plates, locking plate fixation and hemiarthroplasty which have shown to have mixed results. There is a significant heterogeneity among the studies in describing the best surgical procedure in proximal humerus fracture. [6] The present aim of the study is to study the occurrence, mechanism of injury and displacement of various types of fracture according to Neer's score system.

The aim of the present study was to assess and compare the functional outcome with different modalities in fixation of proximal humerus shaft fractures.

Materials and Methods

The present retrospective study was conducted in the Department of Orthopaedics, Sheikh Bhikhari Medical College, Hazaribagh for a period of 1 year. 50 cases who fulfilled the inclusion criteria were enrolled. The study participants were informed about the study details and informed written

consent was obtained from them. The history of injury of the participants, general condition and any associated soft tissue injury were evaluated. The severity of the injury was assessed to assess local injury and axillary nerve was assessed by examining any anaesthetic patch over lateral aspect of the shoulder.

Inclusion Criteria

All the cases with proximal humerus fractures above 18 years of age and consenting for the study were included. [Neer's classification: grade 2 to Grade 4]. [7]

Exclusion Criteria

Cases with Pathological fractures, with distal neurovascular deficit, poly trauma patients with injury severity score >16, shaft humerus fractures with proximal extension.

Radiological evaluation of all the included cases were done as per the Neer's trauma series which include, AP view of the scapula, lateral "Y" view of the scapula, axillary view and occasionally the velpau view was taken.

All the routine surgical investigations were done on the included cases and anaesthetic fitness was also evaluated. The modality of the treatment was decided based upon the following factors: Neer's classification [grade 2 to grade 4]; presence of humeral head dislocation and comminution; valgus impaction, quality of bone, open or compound fracture and age of the patient. General anaesthesia was used in all the patients. One of the following methods was used as treatment in all the cases.

- Closed reduction and percutaneous K-wires fixation.
- Open reduction and Internal fixation with K - wire.
- Open reduction and internal fixation with ethibond sutures.
- Open reduction and internal fixation with locking compression plates.
- Closed reduction and internal fixation by Intra-medullary nail.
- Shoulder hemiarthroplasty.

Postoperative care and follow-up

The operated limb was immobilized in arm pouch and mobilization was started in 2nd week with shoulder wheel exercises as per patient's tolerance. Post-operative radiological evaluation was done to assess reduction and stability of fixation. Gentle passive forward flexion and internal and external rotation exercises by end of 3rd week and active exercises by 4th to 6th week were done. Patients were followed on OPD basis at the end of 6 weeks to one year and full functional evaluation with range of movements and function was assessed and

recorded. Results were evaluated for each case based on Neer's shoulder score based on pain, function, range of motion and anatomy. The maximum points are 100 and on overall score the patient's outcome was grouped as excellent >89

units; satisfactory 80-89 units; unsatisfactory 70-79 units and failure <70 units.

The data was analysed using Microsoft excel and presented in number and percentages.

Results

Table 1: Demographic data among the cases in the study

Distribution of cases	N	%
Age wise (years)		
≤18-40	16	32
41-60	23	46
>61	11	22
Gender		
Male	24	48
Female	26	52
Side of fracture		
Right	18	36
Left	32	64
Type of fracture		
Closed	42	84
Open	8	16
Neers's type of fracture		
2 part	20	40
3 part	13	26
4 part	12	24
Fracture with dislocation	5	10
Cause of injury		
Road traffic accident	30	60
Fall	16	32
Others	4	8

46% of the cases were between 41-60 years with 32% between <18-40 years and 22% of cases >60 years of age. The age range was from 19 to 68 years with a mean age of 48.2 years. 52% of cases were females and 48% were males. 64% of the cases sustained fracture on the left side and 36% on right side. 84% of fractures were of closed type and 16% were open. As per Neer's type of fracture classification, the most common type of fracture

observed in our study cases was two-part fracture accounting to 40% of cases followed in order by three part (26%), four part observed in 24% of cases. 5 cases (10%) had fracture dislocation. Road traffic injury was the most common mechanism for injury in 60% of cases and next was a history of fall in 32% of cases and one case was electric shock and other was hit by an iron rod.

Table 2: Distribution of surgical management among the cases in the study

Surgical treatment	N	%
ORIF with LCP	23	46
ORIF with K-wire	6	12
ORIF with K-wire and cancellous screws	3	6
Percutaneous pinning	10	20
Shoulder hemiarthroplasty	2	4
CRIF with intramedullary nailing	4	8
ORIF with ethibond suture	2	4

23 cases (46%) were managed by open reduction and internal fixation with locking compression plate using 4.5 mm cortical screw plates and 6.5 mm cancellous screws. Percutaneous pinning was done in 10 cases (20%). Open reduction with K-wire was done in 6 cases (12%) and open reduction with K-wire and cancellous screws in 3 cases (6%). Closed reduction with intramedullary nailing was done in 4 cases (8%).

Table 3: Distribution of clinical and radiological union among the cases in the study

Distribution of cases	N	%
Clinical union (in weeks)		
11	2	4
12	25	50
13	6	12
14	12	24
15	5	10
Radiological union (in weeks)		
16-18	36	72
19-20	10	20
>20	4	8

Clinical union was observed in 50% of cases by 12 weeks and the average time taken was 13.7 weeks. 72% of cases (36/50) developed radiological union between 16-18 weeks and the average time was 17.93 weeks.

Table 4: Distribution of Neer's score of cases and result in the study

Neer's score	1st week (%)	4th week (%)	8th week (%)	Final (%)	Result
<70	50 (100)	36 (72)	6 (12)	2 (4)	Failure
70-79	0	14 (28)	5 (10)	3 (6)	Unsatisfactory
80-89	0	0	36 (72)	6 (12)	Satisfactory
>90	0	0	3 (6)	38 (76)	Excellent

In the present study, Neer's score was done on patient every 1st week, 4th week, 8th week and finally at 14th week. All the cases (50/50) had score <70 during 1st week, 36 cases (72%) in 4th week, 6 cases (12%) in 8th week and 2 cases (4%) in 14th final week which was considered as a failure outcome in our study as per Neer's criteria. In 4th week, 14 cases (28%) had score between 70-79, 5 cases (10%) in 8th week and only 3 cases

(6%) in final 14th week which was considered as unsatisfactory outcome. 80-89 score was observed in 36 cases (72%) in 8th week and 6 cases (12%) in 14th week which was considered as satisfactory outcome. >90% score was observed in 3 case (6%) in 8th week and 38 cases (76%) at the final 14th week which was considered as an excellent outcome in the study.

Table 5: Average score of pain, function, ROM and anatomy of cases in the study

Modalities	Min-max	Mean	Median	SD
Pain	29-35	34.6	35	1.68
Function	12-30	23.5	24	3.7
Range of Motion	14-19	16.55	16	1.88
Anatomy	4-10	6.9	8	1.70
Total	59-90	79.65	82	7.63

The mean scores observed on Neer's score were pain (34.6 units), function (23.5 units), range of motion (16.55 units) and anatomy (6.9 units).

Discussion

Proximal humerus fractures comprise nearly 4%-5% of all fracture types and nearly 25% of fracture humerus. These fractures are commonly seen in the elderly population (people aged 60 years or more). The proximal humerus typically breaks into four fragments along the physical lines of fusion - two tuberosities, the humeral head, and the shaft. Most tuberosity fractures take place secondary to the displacement of the head fragment and their degree of spatial displacement is initially minimal, relative to their normal anatomic position. [8] With non-operative management, progressive displacement may occur because of the unopposed pull of the

rotator cuff muscles. Hence, the non-operative management of these displaced fractures is more controversial. Non-operative treatment may result in complications like non union, osteonecrosis, and malunion. Hence, in the majority of cases, operative management becomes mandatory for better outcomes. [9] Over the past 10 years, there has been considerable expansion in the range of reconstructive implants available to treat these injuries. There are different methods of internal fixation using, locking compression plates and screws, percutaneous fixation with metallic k wires and screws, tension band, external fixation, fixed-angle blade plates, transosseous suture fixation, intramedullary device shoulder arthroplasty, but none of these methods have been successful. [10] The management of these fractures can be a significant challenge, especially in the presence of poor cancellous bone due to osteoporosis and

multiple fracture segments resulting in failure of fixation with conventional plating systems. The major goal in the treatment of this fracture is to promote complication-free healing to recreate a pain-free mobile, stable and functional shoulder joint. [11,12]

46% of the cases were between 41-60 years with 32% between <18-40 years and 22% of cases >60 years of age. The age range was from 19 to 68 years with a mean age of 48.2 years. Court-Brown et al reported in their epidemiological study with an average of 66 years, for men 56 and women 70 years. [1] 52% of cases were females and 48% were males. Similar reports were observed in the studies of Nwachukwu et al with male to female sex ratio of 8:12. [13] Road traffic injury was the most common mechanism for injury in 60% of cases and next was a history of fall in 32% of cases and one case was electric shock and other was hit by an iron rod. This finding of our study was consistent to many studies in the literature which also revealed other mechanisms like electric shock, assault by a rod as other mechanisms of injury. In our study, fracture was more common on left side (64%) than right (36%) which was similar to finding of Gerber et al [14] and contrary to the findings of Björkenheim et al. [15] As per Neer's type of fracture classification, the most common type of fracture observed in our study cases was two-part fracture accounting to 40% of cases followed in order by three part (26%), four part observed in 24% of cases which was similar to the findings in the study of Vijayvargiya et al [16] 3 and 4 part fractures were more common than 2 part fractures.

23 cases (46%) were managed by open reduction and internal fixation with locking compression plate using 4.5 mm cortical screw plates and 6.5 mm cancellous screws. Percutaneous pinning was done in 10 cases (20%). Open reduction with K-wire was done in 6 cases (12%) and open reduction with K-wire and cancellous screws in 3 cases (6%). Closed reduction with intramedullary nailing was done in 4 cases (8%). In the present study, Neer's score was done on patient every 1st week, 4th week, 8th week and finally at 14th week. All the cases (50/50) had score <70 during 1st week, 36 cases (72%) in 4th week, 6 cases (12%) in 8th week and 2 cases (4%) in 14th final week which was considered as a failure outcome in our study as per Neer's criteria. In 4th week, 14 cases (28%) had score between 70-79, 5 cases (10%) in 8th week and only 3 cases (6%) in final 14th week which was considered as unsatisfactory outcome. 80-89 score was observed in 36 cases (72%) in 8th week and 6 cases (12%) in 14th week which was considered as satisfactory outcome. >90% score was observed in 3 case (6%) in 8th week and 38 cases (76%) at the final 14th week which was

considered as an excellent outcome in the study. A different study from Gujarat found that excellent results occurred in 54% of instances, satisfactory results in 24% of cases, unsatisfactory results in 12% of cases, and failures occurred in 10% of cases. [17] Ganesan et al [18] also observed excellent results in 50% of the instances, satisfactory results in 30% of the cases, unsatisfactory results in 10% of the cases, and failure results in 10% of the cases. According to a study by Jagiasi et al [19], the results were outstanding in 40% of the instances, very good in 6.66%, good in 30%, fair in 20%, and poor in 3.33% of the cases. The results of a study by Vijayanand et al [20] were excellent outcomes in 23 cases, satisfactory in four, unsatisfactory in two, and in one case a failure. According to a study by Bansal et al [21], the results were excellent in 16% of the instances, good in 44%, fair in 16%, and poor in 24% of the patients. The mean scores observed on Neer's score were pain (34.6 units), function (23.5 units), range of motion (16.55 units) and anatomy (6.9 units).

Than as et al [22] reported an impingement rate of 5.5% in a comprehensive review of 12 studies on proximal humerus fractures. Seven per cent (3/41) of respondents reported stiffness. All of these patients were over 65, had diabetes, and were discovered to have neglected to perform the recommended postoperative physical therapy exercises. Only one patient (2%) out of the total had a surface infection that needed to be treated with intravenous antibiotics. Brunner et al [23] and Agudelo et al [24] observed infection rates of 2% and 4.5%, respectively, in their trials.

Conclusion

The present study concluded that good surgical skills, surgeons experience in selection of the type of surgery depending upon the factors like type of fracture are necessary to achieve correct and best outcome. Clinical evaluation, obtaining proper radiological views, age of the patient and activity holds the key for realistic approach and surgical management of complex humerus fractures. Proper patient selection and thorough knowledge of the anatomy and biomechanical principles are the pre-requisites for a successful surgery and good functional outcome.

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